

Dataverse Deposit Workflow

This document provides an overview, in outline format, of a standard workflow for creating and depositing FAIR datasets in Dataverse.

Repository link: <https://dataverse.harvard.edu/>

Dataverse User Guide: <https://guides.dataverse.org/en/latest/user/>

Dataverse Data Model:

Dataverse Deposit Workflow:

This workflow assumes that all users are active Harvard affiliates with HarvardKey credentials.

- I. Create account/login
 - A. Regardless of whether you have a Harvard Dataverse user account, click on the **login** button in the upper right hand corner of the page
 1. If not already selected, find Harvard University in the **Login with My Institution** option. Click submit. You will be directed to the HarvardKey login platform.
 2. Once logged in, if you do not have a user account in Dataverse already, you will be prompted to create one at this point.
- II. Create collection: in order to utilize many of the FAIR data features in Dataverse, one may wish to create a collection or “container” for their datasets. Datasets in one collection can be linked easily to another collection to better support discovery.
 - A. Click “Add Data” and then “New Dataverse”
 - B. Create Page (aka “General Info”)
 1. Add basic collection metadata (owner, type, etc.)
 2. ID is used to generate a unique URL for your collection. It can be useful to create something that is human readable here.
 3. Description - this text box accepts a small number of HTML markup tags that can be used to format this space. Use this field to describe the basic

contents of this collection. Consider including links to labs, publications, profiles/portfolios, and other online locations or websites that are relevant to the datasets published here.

C. Choose metadata & facets

1. The basic “citation metadata” is generally fine to use. This is where you may want to add the option to use additional metadata, such as life sciences or geographic.
2. One major reason to add more specific metadata fields is to facilitate searchability of your data.
3. Any metadata field can also be added as a facet. For example, you may want to add “species” if you plan to add dozens of datasets for many different animal species and want to give users the ability to sort your list of datasets by “species.”

III. Curate data files (**External**)

- A. Organize directories & files for reuse (download from Canon and/or other external file store). Aim to archive non-proprietary file formats where possible (eg. CSV vs Excel for tabular data, .tiff or jpg vs .czi or .lei for microscopy image files)
 1. Identify total size of dataset. All files in total, and largest individual file size.
 2. Review requirements and best practices for **reuse**.
- B. Code and analysis scripts
 1. Save notebooks and other scripts as markdown files or other simple, interoperable file formats.
 2. If all pipeline documentation is in a notebook format, make note of this to disclose in file metadata or dataset description.
- C. Draft documentation and/or README for this dataset. It can be easiest to draft a basic template for yourself with reusable information that can be customized for each dataset.
 1. Datasheets for datasets: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1803.09010>
 2. Countway Library README guidance: <https://datamanagement.hms.harvard.edu/collect-analyze/documentation-metadata/readme-files>

IV. Create dataset and edit draft

- A. Navigate to your collection and click “Add Data” -> “New Dataset.” Fill out the basic deposit form and upload simple, small files via UI (drag and drop). Click “Save Dataset” to save the dataset as a new draft.
- B. Add rich metadata by using the “Edit” -> “Metadata” menu on your dataset draft page.
 1. [ORCID](#)s for author
 2. Funding information
 3. Related publications
 4. Links to other data in Related Dataset.

5. **Question:** What metadata schemas do genomics researchers use (at the dataset level)?
- C. Terms of Use
 1. CC0 for all non-sensitive, open data.
 2. **Question:** What data type or reuse case might require a special license and/or custom Terms of Use statement?
- V. Add files
- A. Via UI for small to medium file sizes. Drag and drop, “choose files” uploader, or Dropbox integration.
 - B. For GitHub users, consider using the [Dataverse GitHub Action](#) to directly transfer data and code files into a dataset on Harvard Dataverse.
 - C. For larger files and/or to upload directories with many files:
 1. Enable “direct upload” if necessary by reaching out to support@dataverse.harvard.edu or katherine_mika@harvard.edu. Direct upload bypasses the typical ingest process for data files. It is necessary for uploading large directories via the DVUploader or large archived file formats (.tar.gz or .zip). **Note:** Directories compressed into .zip files are automatically unpacked and indexed as individual files in Dataverse. To avoid this, you may either request Direct Upload be enabled on your collection OR you can “double zip” the .zip file OR use a different compression/archiving protocol (eg. .tar.gz, .7zip, etc.)
 2. Choose between the [java dvuploader](#) or [python dvuploader](#) (direct upload) to programmatically upload files to a dataverse dataset.
 - D. To publish and archive “large data” (>2TB or so), you must [reach out directly](#) to the Harvard Dataverse team for specific guidance and permissions.
 - E. Restricted files - for files that may not be made publicly available, you may either *Restrict access* or *Embargo* them by selecting the files using the check boxes on the Files tab and clicking “Edit Files.”
 1. Restrict: From the “Edit files” button on the files tab of the dataset page you can restrict files from being downloaded once the dataset is published. You may or may not choose to enable the “request access” button for restricted files. When using this feature, keep in mind any licensing or Terms of Use issues that may affect a dataset with files that may not be openly shared.
 2. Embargo: From the “Edit Files” button choose “Embargo” to add a date of access for when the data should be made available in the future.
- VI. Manage Access & Permissions
- A. Basic sharing with contributors or collaborators:
 1. All datasets inherit user access permissions from the Collection they are stored inside. For example, if your lab collection that you created a dataset inside of has given you and all other members *curator* status to the collection space, all members will have *curator* level access to your dataset also. To manage Collection permissions, you can use the “Edit” -> “Permissions” button from the Collection page.

2. To give separate permissions to specific users for a dataset, use the “Edit” -> “Permissions” button from the dataset page. Choose “Dataset” to edit permissions for the whole dataset, and choose “Files” to manage specific permissions for restricted files.

B. Preview URL & Anonymous Review:

1. You can create a **Preview URL**, using the “Edit” -> “Preview URL” button, for a draft version of your dataset that allows you to share your dataset (for viewing and downloading of files) before it is published to a wide group of individuals who may not have a user account on the Dataverse installation. Anyone you send the Preview URL to will not have to log into the Dataverse installation to view the unpublished dataset.
2. An **Anonymous URL**, also accessed from the “Edit” -> “Preview URL” button, is a link to your dataset draft that supports anonymous review by removing author names and other potentially identifying information from citations, version history tables, and some metadata fields. To verify that all identifying information has been removed or anonymized, it is recommended that you logout and review the dataset as it would be seen by an anonymized Preview URL user. **NOTE: this feature is planned to be added to Harvard Dataverse in the Summer of 2025.**

VII. Publish Dataset: When all files are added and metadata is complete, you can publish your dataset by navigating to its draft page and clicking “Publish Dataset.” **Once published, a dataset cannot be deleted.** Keep in mind that you may keep a dataset in draft status for as long as you may need to while working on a project or paper.

- A. Versioning: You can always make changes and edits to the metadata and files, but keep in mind that all revisions are tracked as new versions. All edits trigger the creation of a new “draft” that must be published again in order to update the dataset. Keep in mind that complete copies of files are kept in previous versions, meaning that if you change a file, you double the storage cost for that file.
- B. Deaccessioning: It is not possible to delete a dataset in Dataverse, due to commitments made by you as an author and by Harvard Dataverse as a data repository when a DOI is registered. You may, however, deaccession specific versions of a dataset. This removes files and most metadata from being accessed by users. A “landing page” is maintained to indicate that this data was published with this specific DOI, but the content is no longer available. The deaccession option is available under the “Edit” menu on a dataset.

VIII. Other tools

- A. Github connection: <https://github.com/marketplace/actions/dataverse-uploader-action>
- B. Large data support: <https://support.dataverse.harvard.edu/large-data-support>